

The Limits of Moral Turing Tests

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1 Measuring Moral Capabilities

The moral admissibility and most likely the acceptance of highly autonomous artificial agents in hard- and software requires a sufficient level of moral competency. The moral argument for this claim can be stated in short in the following line of reasoning: Autonomous artificial agents perform at least some actions that would otherwise be done by human agents. Unlike fully controlled machines – such as a manually operated crane, a human-driven car, or a vending machine – the machine’s behavior is not determined in its entirety by a human agent. Furthermore, we legitimately expect from a human agent to be generally morally competent. Hence, we can also legitimately expect for a machine (semi)autonomously executing such actions to be morally competent.

A few remarks are in place on this argument. First, it only states a necessary, not a sufficient conditions for deploying such machines. Compensation for a displaced work force or similar measures might be necessary to fully justify the use of (semi)autonomous artificial agents. Second, the argument does not require the machines to have precisely the same level of competency of the human agent they’re pre-empting. Other factors may require the machine to be more or less morally competent than its human counterpart.

Finally, and most importantly, the notion of moral competency is presupposed to be well-understood. However, in the following I will argue that it is in fact not. To this end, I shall utilize the idea of a moral Turing test (MTT), as discussed by several authors (Wallach and Allen, 2008; Allen et al., 2000).

2 Moral Turing Tests

The key idea of a moral Turing test, taken from its namesake, the Turing test for intelligence, is not to try to state the conditions of moral competency

explicitly, but instead use a human test person as the yardstick. I won't get into some of the fundamental limitations of Turing tests, such as presupposing linguistic capabilities. Those still apply, but more interesting are the issues particular to a moral Turing test.

There are multiple versions of the MTT, so I will for brevity stick to the simplest one in this abstract: A human agent and a machine are both confronted with moral problems, presumably typical dilemmas (cf. Anderson et al. (2006) for a study using fairly realistic dilemmas). The human and the machine both pass their judgment, and those are presented to an observer. If the observer fails to recognize which responses are human and which artificial, the machine passes the test; it counts as a moral agent as competent as a human.

The first and most obvious problem for this approach is the prevalence of moral disagreement. If the observer happens to hold fundamentally different values than the human judge in the setup, the machine may easily be attributed more moral competency. But unless we assume the observer is correct in their judgment and the judge is not, this seems to be a measure not of a capability to pass correct judgment, but rather a comparative measure of disagreement.

A possible response to this is to require not only the resulting judgment, but also the underlying reasoning to be presented. The observer could then rely more on the form of the moral reasoning rather than its – potentially controversial – content. This approach, however, comes with a number of new problems. Setting aside problems for both the human and the artificial agent to lay down their reasoning comprehensively, the observer now has two kinds of information: On the one hand, there are the substantial values and judgment, on the other there is the formal structure of the underlying reasoning. While before, in our simple version, the observer had only one piece of information and we were rather clear on the basis of their judgment, now an observer could use any combination of those two pieces of information. But presumably, not every combination will constitute a reasonable measure of moral competency. If it were, we could just return to the simple test, because discounting the additional information entirely would be one of the arbitrary weighings of the two kinds of information.

This hints at the underlying philosophical issue that MTTs expose: It is not clear at all whether we mean a grasp of substantial moral values and judgment when speaking of moral competency, or rather the formal capacity to reason from any set of such values and judgments. The simple MTT, implicitly, defines moral competency as being able to make the same substantial judgments as the observer. But that is an incoherent conception of moral competency if, because of the prevalence of disagreement, different observers

would come to opposing conclusions on the competency of our artificial moral agent.

This line of reasoning assumes that moral customization is not an admissible option. Otherwise, the observer dependence of competency attributions could simply be translated into equipping machines with the values of their owner or user. This seems to be an acceptable path when it comes to something like customizing a machine to handle the linguistic idiosyncracies of its user, but it leads to absurdity in the case of morality. Imagine an autonomous vehicle that shares the values of its reckless driver, or an automatic trader that realizes the locust-like greed of its master; those would be no less justified to perform harmful actions than their user or owner.

These examples of selfish users may lead the reader to think of the idea of introducing some version of the veil of ignorance (Rawls, 1958) to prevent such issues. The veil of ignorance imposes a standard of neutrality, in the sense that the person behind the veil cannot identify whom they will be in the scenario they are morally evaluating. However, while this may block the realization of selfishness, it does not resolve the problem of moral disagreement. It only could do so if all disagreement were reducible to selfishness; but one can easily construct a plausible counterexample.

Imagine a person who is strongly in favor of paternalism, but accepts a paternalistic treatment themselves. Other people, though, clearly reject strong forms of paternalism, also when applied to others. Unless we assume all such cases are due to some form of irrationality, anonymity won't solve the problem.

The next logical step, if a neutrality condition fails, is to use a collection of observers to pass judgment as a group. Thereby, disagreement is not sidestepped by the MTT, but would have to be resolved within. This is a promising suggestion, however, it is well-known that judgment and preference aggregation are threatened by impossibility results (cf. List et al. (2011) for a case in point). So the major open question of a social MTT (sMTT) becomes to choose an aggregation procedure and impose conditions on it that are morally satisfactory and logically satisfiable.

To conclude this brief abstract, MTTs cannot sidestep the serious moral questions raised by the increasing autonomy of artificial agents. This is not to say that they cannot teach us significant insights regarding our judgments or those of machines. Setting up an sMTT would require us to make explicit some of our assumptions about how we are to handle moral disagreements in general. But without further assumptions or requirements, an MTT cannot measure a capacity worthy of the name moral competency.¹

¹This also raises the question, as with the concept of general intelligence, if there is a

References

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coherent concept of moral competency. At this point, I cannot adjudicate this issue with any certainty.